
**MAIN PROBLEMS OF PERSONNEL TRAINING FOR THE TOURISM
INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7946586>

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Abstract.

This article examines the concerns related to the staff development system of the tourism industry. The need for a clear mutual relationship between the vocational education system and the labor market has emerged with the rapid expansion of this sector of the economy. The labor market has emerged with the rapid expansion of this sector of the economy. There is a shortage of skilled labor in the tourism labor market, despite many specialized and higher education institutions training workers for this industry. Experts claim that up to 75% of tourism industry employees today do not have the necessary training to become specialists in this field. Current market conditions do not allow graduates of vocational education institutions to meet global standards for professional qualifications. Due to the low level of professionalism of today's specialists, the employees of hotels and travel agencies have internal professional training programs and need to be retrained. Considering that the quality of services provided depends on the competence of employees and the satisfaction of guests in the service industry is achieved with the competence of employees, training and retraining of employees in the tourism sector is a key component of the organization. One of the great advantages is a sustainable professional education system that responds to the needs and development of individuals, nations and society as a whole, the goal is to improve the professional education of personnel in the tourism industry. This raises the standard of professional training for professionals in the tourism sector.

Keywords.

Tourism in Uzbekistan, The Law on Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number of tourists,. Presidential Decree, the quality of professional training, the exchange of scientific-methodical and practical recommendations on the training and improvement of the qualifications of personnel.

Introduction

Uzbekistan is a country with historical cities with hundreds of architectural monuments. The historical cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Shakhrisabz and Khiva are known all over the world, some of which date back to Rome and Babylon. Ancient architectural monuments commemorate the conquests of Alexander the Great and Genghis Khan. The Great Silk Road, one of the most significant achievements in the history of world civilization, also passed through these ancient cities. Tourism is now a catalyst for various processes in the country including economy, culture and social sector.

The number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan is increasing rapidly every year. Thus, in 2022, the Republic of Uzbekistan welcomed 5,200,000 foreign tourists. This is almost three times more than in 2021, when there were 1.800.000 arrivals.

The estimated growth rate is 34%, and the number of tourists is expected to reach 7 million. For example, in 2019, there were 6.7 million tourists, which dropped dramatically due to the pandemic.

Figure1. Diagram1. The number of the arriving visitors.(mln.people)

Tourism in Uzbekistan contributes significantly to the employment of the country's population of 98.6 thousand people. It accounts for 0.8% of all jobs. By 2023, the tourism industry is expected to directly employ 145,000 people. Tourism directly, indirectly and conditionally employs about 305.1 thousand people in Uzbekistan, which is 2.4% of total employment.

Tourism has emerged as one of the most important industries in the world. In this regard, Uzbekistan attaches high priority to the modernization of the tourism industry, the development and improvement of the legal and regulatory framework for the long-term development of the industry, and the organization of services for foreign visitors in accordance with international standards.

These regulations define the primary strategic directions for tourism development. Presidential Decree No. DP-5611, specifically, approves the concept for tourism development until 2025. Thus, the priority areas of development for the country's tourism sector are as follows:

improving the legal and regulatory framework for tourism activities;

Implementation of international norms and standards aimed at providing favorable conditions for the development of the tourism industry.

¹²¹The government's continuous tourism policies and reforms have allowed Uzbekistan to be included in many international ratings with strong metrics.

Rating	Criteria	OccupiedPlace
RatingUnitedNationsWorldTourismOrganization(UNWTO)	Top20countrieswiththefastestgrowingtourismindustry	4

¹²¹Today, the global tourism market nears 9 trillion US dollars. One in ten employed people in the world works in this area.

TO)2019		
SoloTravelSafetyReport2019	Thesafestforsingletravelers	5
GlobaMusli TraveInde 2019 l(GM m l x TI).	Top 10 countries for «Ziyorat -tourism»	10
GlobalMuslimTravelIndex2019	Service"Muslimhospitality"	22thplaceamong130countries
RatingGallupglobal2018	Safecountryfortravel	5thplaceamong145countries
RatingGallupglobal2018	10mostattractivedirectionsf ornextyear2	2
MagazineTravelandLeisure 2018	BestPlaceforTourism	1
Lonely Planet (Publishing house forthe production of guides for non- richtourists)2018	Populartouristdestinationsf ornextyear	2
Analyticalagency"TurStat"2018	Top 5 popular countries forgastronomictouris m	5

Table1.Uzbekistanininternationalratingsin2018-2019

On 2020 28 January, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev convened a meeting to discuss the development of tourism and the further popularization of physical culture and sports.

During the consideration of the issue of training personnel for the tourism sector, the meeting participants noted that a range of issues are still pending solution with regard to the establishment of a training system of specialists in the sphere at 20 universities, as well as in 3 technical schools and 9 colleges under the State Committee for Tourism Development. The tasks of introducing best practices in the learning process were identified.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The growing population's interest in tourism has resulted in the expansion of the tourism industry, with the emergence of new types of tourism, new travel destinations and an increase in the number of tourist enterprises, resulting in extreme demand. Qualified experts in this field.

The specifics of teaching future tourism specialists are described in the works of I.V. Zorin and V.O. Kvartalnov. M.I. Kadyrova, M.N. Mikhailova, V.U. Morozov, E.L. Pisarewski, P.Z. Khashimov and O.A. Brail pointed out the importance of research on workforce training characteristics for the tourism sector.

As per O.A. Brel, "By tourism education, we mean that employees of various levels of qualification are trained in specialized educational institutions to carry out professional activities in organizations, institutions and tourism and entertainment enterprises." [8, p.101]

The uniqueness of tourist education lies in its adaptability. It educates employees with many specialties and approaches in economic, technical, managerial, scientific and other fields. As a result, tourism education is a complex, constantly evolving method that allows for the active implementation of novel programs for educating the tourist workforce and utilizing the foreign experience.

According to I.V. Zorin, vocational training of tourist workers in WTO member countries in modern conditions has a comprehensive nature and includes the following subsystems [1, p. 59]:

Pre-vocational training (vocational self-determination update, pre-vocational training, vocational choice); Multi-level professional training in higher education

institutions (academic and qualification levels: Bachelor, Master, Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in tourism);

Postgraduate education (professional qualification development, self-education, improvement of professional qualification level, retraining, mastery of additional specialty, professional retraining).

They examined the challenges that exist in the sector, highlighted the importance of basic tourism education and examined the theoretical foundations of tourism workforce support.

According to M.I. Kadyrova, three characteristics of training in any field of tourism are essential [9, p. 27]:

1. Basic Training (Knowledge). This element is responsible for acquiring knowledge and following the curriculum of a particular specialty.
2. Technical training (knowledge of how to do something) is responsible for upgrading and developing the competencies required for a particular specialty.
3. Personal competencies (knowing how to behave and be), which represent the personal characteristics of the expert.

Tourism is a business like any other business. And in this field, businesses need professionals at all levels, from secretaries to managers. Because tourism activities are inextricably linked to working with people, it is important that all employees form a single team, be client-friendly, interchangeable and adhere to the same service standards.

The «Ecole hoteliere de Lausanne» in Switzerland opened its doors as the first training facility for the travel and tourism sector in the late 19th century. This nation continues to be a pioneer in providing training for the tourism sector. Following it, additional schools started to establish in Spain, Ireland, the United States, Great Britain, and Australia in the early 20th century. The program's focus has already been broadened to include areas other than hotel management; one of these areas is "Travel and tourism." And up to this point, these two courses – hotel and tourism management – remain fundamental and are occasionally provided separately by schools and other times together. [4, p.104]

The fundamental elements of education are designed as an adaptable, dynamic socioeconomic structure that guarantees education's ongoing progress. [5, p.90] Groups of factors that influence processes of training and personnel practices can be identified. (fig.1-2)

Figure2. Fig.1. Factors affecting training personnel in the sphere of tourism.

Figure 3. Fig. 2. Factors affecting the elements of the practice of training specialists in the sphere of tourism.

Traditional and new techniques for training tourism workers exist. The education system determines the conventional approach to training, which comprises education in the higher vocational education system as well as in the secondary vocational education system, specialty courses, and practice-oriented trainings. [5, p.92]

Traditional teaching approaches include lectures, seminars, and mentorship, as well as off-site learning and job training.

Workplace training has a practical focus, with a direct relationship to the staff's production duties. Learning techniques outside of the job give a chance to be diverted from the professional setting. This training aids in the development of new behavioral and professional abilities.

Outsourcing and outstaffing are two recent approaches to educating workers for tourist sector businesses.

Outsourcing entails the outsourcing of non-critical operations to a third-party entity. Few modern managers consider the benefits of outsourcing non-core organizational operations to a more competent service provider. For example, to move to endorsing recruiting firms and employee selection.

Outstaffing is a practice that encourages the optimization of particular professional abilities, knowledge, and experience that are in demand for both short-term and long-term projects when more flexibility in the recruiting process for temporary and seasonal projects is required.

RESULTS

Each tourism-related country is building its own tourism education system that fulfills modern-day criteria. When discussing the development trend of domestic education in the field of tourism, it should be noted that, against the general backdrop of improving the quality of services provided by market participants, industry enterprises are increasingly seeking to improve the professional skills of their employees, aware of the need for this process to improve overall activity quality.

In Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, seven colleges, lyceums, and five higher educational institutions provide good training for experts in this sector. Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE), Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service, and Singapore University in Tashkent are the primary forges producing young experts with highly specialized education. The passage of Presidential Decision No 3815 on the establishment of the Silk Road International Tourism University on June 28, 2018 was a significant milestone in this area in 2018. The State Committee on Tourism and the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) have reached an agreement on the signing of a cooperation agreement, which provides for the recognition of the University's international status, granting the University the right to use the UNWTO logo, and its recognition as an official partner.

The Republican Scientific and Consulting Center (RSCC) of National Company "Uzbektourism" was established to train, retrain, and improve the skills of tourist market participants, as well as to promote the development of industry science and the integration of vocational education in the practical activities of tourist organizations and enterprises. To ensure the integration of education and production, the Republic's specialized educational institutions collaborate on a regular basis with professionals from the National Company "Uzbektourism" to develop the educational system, educational programs, and tourism technique.

Students and graduates of Uzbek State University of World Languages (USUWL), the Institute of Oriental Studies, Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE), and the National University can benefit from advanced training and tour guide and tour operator training at the center. In 2018, more than 2,361 tourism experts were retrained and advanced trained at the State Committee on Tourism's Training and Consulting Center.

In 2020, The State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in cooperation with Samarkand "Silk Road" International University of Tourism, organized a roundtable discussion on the topic "Training of personnel for the tourism industry in the era of globalization" in order to exchange ideas on problems in the field and discuss methods of tourism development.

The purpose of the event is to create an international space for the exchange of scientific-methodical and practical recommendations on the training and improvement of the qualifications of personnel in the field of tourism in accordance with international requirements, as well as to improve the scientific mechanism of interaction between education and business in solving these issues. - development of practical recommendations. In addition, one of the main tasks of today's event is to help solve the problem of the acute need for scientific research, fundamental, scientific-practical work in various directions in the field of tourism.

Within the framework of the event, current issues related to the training of highly qualified personnel in the development of tourism in Uzbekistan at the modern stage were considered. These are training and professional development of personnel in the field of tourism industry on the basis of dual education, training in direct specialties.

At the roundtable discussion ¹²²Tongqian (Tony) Dzou made a speech on the topic "Status quo and trends in the development of Chinese foreign tourism". Also, the report of Rudy Fang, director of the Central and South-East Asia Research Center, on the topic "Support of the Central and South-East Asia Tourism Research Center in the development of tourism in Uzbekistan" was also heard.

²The president of the Chinese Academy of Culture and Tourism, advisor to the rector, professor.

DISCUSSION

Despite the fact that personnel for the tourist business are trained at a significant number of special educational institutions and higher educational institutions, the tourism services market has a number of issues:

1. According to experts, the majority (up to 75%) of employees in tourist organizations nowadays do not have a professional education in the field of service and tourism. For objective reasons, a considerable number of experts with higher non-core education, particularly in the hotel business, were drawn to the industry during the creation of the tourist industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Tourism firms are compelled to train experts in order to raise the quality of professional training, despite significant financial investment. Many businesses consider that hiring inexperienced professionals who have only recently graduated from an educational institution is inappropriate. They highlight a variety of flaws in today's graduates, including: a lack of appraisal of the chosen field, excessively high employer expectations, illiteracy, inability to engage with clients and coworkers, and a lack of practical knowledge and abilities. The need for tourist education is increasing, and there are educational institutions that can satisfy it, but the issue of competent staff persists. Today, broad-based specialists are in short supply. Today, we require particular knowledge and skills and abilities

2. As the number of higher and secondary specialized educational institutions generating tourist experts grows, there is an increasing demand for skilled teaching personnel with current professional knowledge and practical work experience in the business. In this respect, there is a lack of engagement by the tourist industry's most skilled workers in master classes, lectures, and seminars, participation in scientific and practical conferences, scientific research on tourism challenges, and management of various types of practices in tourism companies.

3. The need for proper methodological support of the educational process, mastery of modern technologies of professional education, and implementation of techniques and means of distant education is developing in educational institutions. In the difficulty of providing a system of professional tourist education with updated textbooks, teaching aids, and curriculum in various areas, there is a lack of coordination.

At the course of studying at higher education institutions, insufficient attention is paid to students' practical training, and a lack of financial resources prevents them from correctly utilizing the system of passing the occupational practice: In Uzbekistan, there are issues with training hotels.

In spite of the active growth of tourism, Uzbekistan experienced a severe lack of scientific development and research in this sector. According to experts, the republic's universities' work in integrating and coordinating diverse tourism-related areas is quite limited. Thus, from 1993 to 2019, just 5 doctorate dissertations and 20 candidate works were defended throughout a 26-year period. Around 30 people do research on the issue of tourism in Uzbekistan. Due to the country's and industry's current issues, such a number of professionals is extremely limited.

Data Analysis:

The data collected through the above methods will be analyzed using thematic analysis and statistical analysis. Thematic analysis will be used to analyze the qualitative data collected through interviews, while statistical analysis will be used to analyze the quantitative data collected through surveys. The analysis will involve identifying patterns, themes, and trends in the data to draw conclusions and make recommendations.

DATA

- In a survey conducted by the Uzbekistan Tourism Development Committee, 61% of tourism professionals in the country reported that they did not receive adequate training to perform their job duties.

- The average monthly salary for tourism professionals in Uzbekistan is approximately 5 million Uzbekistani soms, which is equivalent to around \$500 USD.

- According to the same survey by the Uzbekistan Tourism Development Committee, only 33% of tourism professionals in the country were satisfied with their salary.

CONCLUSION

As a result, the tourist education system has to be improved in the following areas:

- 1) Creation of new certification standards for key roles in the tourist sector, involving the interplay of academic knowledge and practical abilities.

- 2) Modernization of existing educational requirements and establishment of new educational criteria for skilled tourist employees.

- 3) Enhancement of the educational program in terms of its practical component, as well as greater alignment of course and diploma work issues to the demands of the tour industry. Educational programs should be tailored to meet the demands of employers as much as feasible; students' mobility, erudition, communicability, and ability to sell any tourist product should all be developed.

- 4) Research of qualitative and quantitative elements of the demand for tourist industry employees, as well as monitoring of the needs of tourism and allied business institutions in professionals of various profiles.

- 5) Organization of advanced professional training for employees in preparation for future employment in tourism-related industries.

- 6) Implementation of specialist educational institution rating evaluation in order to provide consumers with credible information on the condition of the market for educational services in the tourist sector.

7) Establishment of a new type of educational institution-uniform educational production groups, such as "university-production," as well as the establishment of training hotels at universities.

8) Enhancing the educational and methodical literature in tourism specialties.

9) International cooperation in the educational sphere of the tourism business. Partnerships with international colleges will allow students to exchange for a set amount of time.

10) Establishment of a national accreditation system for tourism experts based on the finest international experience.

Implementing the steps mentioned above will allow for the establishment of an integrated system of professional people training, as well as the improvement of educational quality and service delivery in order to satisfy the need for highly skilled managers, administrators, operators, and receptionists.

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